

REVIEW OF HISTORIANS' CHRONICLES OF THE 14th - 16th CENTURY ON AMIR TIMUR'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE URBAN DEVELOPMENT OF SAMARKAND

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Abstract. *The article highlights the scientific works of historians, chroniclers, and great minds who lived, created, and traveled the Middle East and Central Asia meticulously keeping diaries of their observations in the 14th–16th centuries. The value of the historical chronicles by medieval authors, who dedicated years to studying the history, development, and establishment of the Timurid dynasty — its traditions, military campaigns, victorious conquests, culture, architecture, and garden art — is undeniable.*

Keywords: *historians, chroniclers, Amir Timur's gardens, Middle East, Central Asia, Timurids, Samarkand, 14th–16th centuries.*

Introduction: The value of historical chronicles by medieval authors historians, chroniclers and great minds who traveled, meticulously recording their observations in diaries during their journey to the Middle East and Central Asia in 14th–16th centuries, who dedicated years of work to the history of the establishment and flourishing of the Amir Timur dynasty, their traditions and customs, military affairs, victorious campaigns, culture, architecture, and garden art, cannot be overestimated. Ibn Arabshah, Hafizi Abru, Tohir Khoja, Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, Zainiddin Mahmud Wasifi, Ghiyas al-Din Ali, Abu Ishaq al-Farisi al-Istakhri, Ruy Gonzalez de Clavijo, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, Mirkhwand, Ibn Battuta, Khwandamir, and Dawlatshah Samarkandi. Without their works, it would be impossible today to reconstruct a complete picture of the events and historical facts of the Timurids' era.

Main Part: It is noteworthy that many medieval authors cite each other, shedding light on even more invaluable historical works. Scientists who made great contributions to the development of the culture and art of the Middle East are: Mirzo Ulugbek, Ali Qushchi, and Qadi-zade Rumi. Philosophers-poets such as: Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Lutfi, Sakkaki, and Atayi. Artists like Behzad, Qasim Ali, Mirak Naqqash, and Mahmud Muzahhib. Calligraphers: Sultanali Mashhadi, Sultan Muhammad Handan, Muhammad bin Nur, and Darvish Muhammad Taqi also contributed significantly.

One of the earliest Arab descriptions of Samarkand is found in Ibn al-Faqih's *Kitab al-Buldan*, which states: "*Samarkand was built by Iskandar (Alexander the Great), its walls span twelve farsakhs in circumference. It had twelve gates, and from gate to gate the distance is one farsakh. At the top of the walls were battlements and war towers, all twelve gates were wooden and two-leafed. The suburbs and irrigated lands stretch over six thousand jeribs, and the wall surrounded the villages, gardens, and orchards*" [1].

Ibn Battuta praised Samarkand: "*one of the largest and most beautiful cities. It was located on the bank of the Wadi al-Kassar River (the river of washers), from which waterwheels (naurs) lift water to irrigate the gardens. After the evening prayer, residents of the city gathered by the*

river to relax and take a walk. There were platforms for sitting and stalls for selling fruits and other goods. By the river there were grand palaces, showcasing the exceptional craftsmanship of Samarkand's inhabitants. Unfortunately, all these buildings, and the city itself, were fallen into ruins (in 12th century by Chinggis Khan invasions)- there are no more intact walls and gates left, but within the city gardens were remained. The people of Samarkand are kind and hospitable to foreigners, even more than the people of Bukhara" [2]. (Fig. 1)

Merchant Samarkand, at the beginning of the 14th century, was not yet the capital, but it had reached such prosperity that Ibn Battuta ranked it among the largest, most well-maintained, and beautiful Central Asian cities. By the mid-14th century, it was known by major structures such as the Great Mosque, madrasas, and the mausoleum of Kussam ibn Abbas, decorated with exquisite tilework. Amir Timur's extensive construction projects transformed the city into a new capital. His ambitious urban development program reshaped Samarkand into a cultural and commercial hub. The construction of palaces, gardens, and fortifications elevated its significance among the great cities of the East.

Figure 1. Map of the journey of Ibn Battuta 1332-1346 [13].

Al-Istakhri writes: "The center of Samarkand's markets, Ras at-Tak, with streets, markets, and shops adjoining it, is twice as big as all these palaces and gardens. There is no street or house without a garden. If you ascend to the top of the fortress, you cannot see the city's buildings because everything is covered by crowns of garden trees. This city is the port of Maverannahr, where merchants gather. Most of Maverannahr's goods come to Samarkand and from there are distributed to other regions" [4].

From 1403 to 1406 AD, Ruy Gonzalez de Clavijo and Alfonso Paez served as envoys of King of Castile - Enrique III were sent on a diplomatic mission to Amir Timur courtyard (Fig. 2) As Clavijo wrote, "In Samarkand, goods from China, India, Dasht-i Kipchak (Tatarstan) and other places, as well as from the rich kingdom of Samarkand itself, are sold annually. Since there were

no proper rows for convenient trade in the city, Amir Timur ordered a street to be laid out through on both side of the city street, with shops and stalls for the sale of goods" [5] (Fig. 3)

Fig. 2. Map of the journey of Ruy González de Clavijo, ambassador of the King of Castile to the court of Amir Temur, 15th century. / Justin Odum. Using ESRI data, Esri Redlands CA, 2000/

Fig. 3. Plan of Amir Temur to Connect the Fortress Gates by Creating New Trade Streets /Map by Sadikova S.N./

The solid yellow lines indicate the streets and trade passages created by the order of Amir Temur, achieved by demolishing mahallas (residential quarters). The dotted lines show the direction of the planned streets, the construction of which could not be completed due to the death of Amir Temur.

The results and discussion. In 1370, Amir Timur's construction of the capital citadel, towering over the entire area at the center of Hisar, became a key element in the arrangement of the city of Samarkand: here a complex of defensive and governmental buildings was located. "High adobe walls, with rounded sloped edges, massive towers and a crenelated parapet line, surrounded the rectangular fortress (Kal'a). The main streets of the city followed historically established routes were lined with buildings, leading from the center to the gates" [6].

According to M. E. Masson, the official boundary of the city (Hisar) was considered to be the wall with numerous towers (burjs), rebuilt in 773 AH (1371/2 AD), mostly repeating the irregular outline of the old wall from the 11th–12th centuries. Notably, one of the projections of the wall in the northeastern corner was called "Shutur-Gardan," which in Persian means "camel's neck," as it resembled the curve of wall (Fig 4). The width of the city wall was such that one could freely ride a horse on the roof of it, as Mirza Babur did when personally inspecting the defenses during the siege of Samarkand by Shaybani Khan's troops [7].

Figure 4. The map of Samarkand of 15th century / M.E. Masson/ [12].

It is characteristic that Amir Timur sought in every possible way to emphasize the preeminent significance of Samarkand among other Eastern cities. In his view, Samarkand was to become "the world's capital"! For example, Ibn Arabshah, an Arab author, wrote that Amir Timur built several villages near Samarkand, naming them after famous cities with resounding names: "Misr" (Cairo), "Dimashq" (Damascus), "Baghdad," "Sultania," and "Shiraz." These are known to be major cities of the East, the first three of which were capitals of powerful feudal states. As Yakubovskiy mentioned, "this was a political scheme, with which he intended to elevate the authority of his dynasty to an unattainable height in the minds of the people" [5].

By order of Amir Timur, two large four-story buildings were constructed in the Ark (citadel) of Samarkand: Kuk-Saray and Bustan-Saray. The state treasury, workshops, and a prison were located in Kuk-Saray. Bustan-Saray served as the main residence of Amir Timur, under his reign the city streets were rebuilt, and the bazaars were improved. In 1370–1371, the destroyed fortress of Samarkand and its walls, the Shahrستان (citadel) and its six gates were restored, as we find in the historical and topographical sketches of M. E. Masson: "The city of Samarkand, with an area of approximately 4.1 km (including the citadel), had six gates, probably located in the same places where they existed in the 11th–12th-century wall. In any case, in the 14th century, almost a century and a half after the Mongol conquest (12th century), the memory of the former gates was still preserved in local toponyms" [8] (Fig. 5):

Figure 5. The map showing the gates of Medieval Samarkand / the map by S.N. Sadikova /

I. Sheikhzade Gate ("Royal Gate") – These were the northwestern gates, located in the place of the former Namazgoh Gate (in the 11th–12th-century wall);

II. Ahanin Gate ("Iron Gate") – Located to the east, in the northern wall, in the place of the former Bab-ul Khudid Gate (11th–12th centuries), also called the Kusam Mazar Gate, as the road to the revered tomb of the religious figure Kusam ibn Abbas passed through here;

III. Darvozai Firuza ("Turquoise Gate") – These were the only gates on the eastern side, corresponding to the former Meshxed Gate (11th–12th centuries). They may have been named after a nobleman of the early Timurids – Firuz Shah, who was associated with the construction of the "Madrasah of Firuza" on the street of the same name, which led to the gates, or possibly due to the nearby garden of "Bagi Firuza," located southeast of the gates. In the southern wall, there were two gates:

IV. Darvozai Suzangaron ("Needlemakers' Gate") – This gate was likely located in the southern part of the city, where the needle-makers' quarter was situated.

V. Kyarizgokh Gate, later renamed "Khodja Ahrar Gate," since the road through it led to the suburban neighborhood of Khodja Kafshir, where the 15th-century sheikh and prominent statesman Khodja Ahrar resided. Near Kyarizgokh Gate slightly south of the citadel the channel of one of the city's ditches was running in the western wall.

VI. Chorsu Gate ("Four Streams Gate"), also called Chorraha – meaning "Gate of Four Roads," as a network of roads branched out from here in four directions.

The city gates were architecturally designed, with towers on either side of the portal and likely covered with tiles on the outside. From the gates six main street arteries began, which converged approximately in the middle of the city, where the central city bazaars were located. According to Masson: *"These streets, although not straight, with their approximately radial divergence, provided the basic layout of the city. An attempt to expand and straighten them was made shortly before Amir Timur's death when, by his order, work began on cutting a more regular*

path that was planned to run through the entire city from one gate to another (Fig. 3.). The work began at the end of 1404" [8].

It is well known how much importance Amir Timur attached to Samarkand: it was the object of his constant care and attention. Amir Timur clearly understood that the growth of Samarkand as a capital city had political significance. In a certain sense, one can speak of a whole program of construction in Samarkand. The first thing Amir Timur focused on was the development of handicraft production in the city" [5].

The ambassador of the King of Spain to the court of Amir Timur, Ruy González de Clavijo, made numerous descriptions of Samarkand in his travel diary. *"The wealth of Samarkand consists not only in foodstuffs, but also in silk fabrics, satin, taffeta, and tersenal (a type of fabric), of which much is produced there. There are also linings of fur and silk, perfumes, spices, dyes, gold and azure, and other products. That is why the king (Amir Timur) wanted so much to elevate this city. In every country he conquered, he brought people back to Samarkand, especially skilled craftsmen in various trades. From Damascus, he brought craftsmen who made bows and weapons, worked with glass and clay. From Turkey, he brought archers, masons, goldsmiths... He brought engineers and bomb-makers. He gathered so many people from all lands in this city that there were said to be over 150,000 people: Turks, Arabs, Moors, Armenian Christians, Greek Catholics, Nasoreans, and Jacobites. There were so many people that they could not fit in the city, nor on the streets, nor in the villages. Even outside the city, under trees and in caves, there were incredibly many"* [9].

According to U. Alimov: *"Amir Timur dedicated much time and effort to improving his capital, Samarkand, and its surroundings, striving to surpass other cities of the East"* [10]. During Amir Timur's rule, a decision was made to straighten one of the main thoroughfares of Samarkand, running from the Iron Gates (Ahaning) to Registan Square (now Tashkent Street). Such a large-scale, purposeful urban planning project was possible only under a powerful ruler and was unique in its kind (Fig. 3). Later, in 1379, a magnificent garden with the Ak-Saray Palace was built near Shahrisabz. The portal of this palace, 50 meters high, surpassed in scale the colossal Friday Mosque in the city of Tabriz, built by the Ilkhan Oljeitu Khudabanda, as well as the famous vault of the Sassanid palace in Ctesiphon, known as Taq Kasra, which in its time eclipsed all other Sassanid structures and was an architectural challenge for the architects of the East.

According to the historian Hafizi Abru: *"Samarkand, which had previously been built from clay, was rebuilt by Timur with stone buildings."* According to Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi: *"After this, he happily and with good fortune headed toward heaven-like Samarkand. This city, abundant in water, fruits, gardens, and fortresses, envied even by paradise itself, he made his capital and sat there. He built fortresses, pavilions, and palaces. He appointed each beg to oversee tax collection for one master builder. He entrusted Amir Ak Buga with this task. Previously, this city had suffered many disasters and was greatly destroyed. Thanks to the mercy of the ruler Sahib Qiran, when palaces and other buildings were constructed in Samarkand, and gardens were laid out, other cities in the world envied it, and its fame spread far and wide"* [11].

Conclusions: Samarkand during Amir Timur's era became a wealthy, green, beautiful, and densely populated city. Amir Temur's urban planning efforts significantly contributed to the development of Samarkand's infrastructure, transforming it into a thriving commercial and cultural center. His vision involved connecting the city's various fortress gates through the creation of new trade streets, a strategic move aimed at fostering commerce and improving the overall layout of the city. As the map by Sadikova S.N. illustrates, solid yellow lines represent the streets and trade

passages that were successfully created by demolishing residential quarters (mahallas). This bold move not only facilitated smoother movement within the city but also helped integrate trade and craftsmanship into the urban landscape. However, the dotted lines indicate planned streets whose construction remained incomplete due to the death of Sahibkiran Amir Temur.

This ambitious urban planning initiative highlights foresight in urban development, prioritizing commerce and efficient city design to establish Samarkand as a key hub in the region. Despite the challenges posed by his passing, the framework he set in motion laid the groundwork for Samarkand's enduring prosperity. His approach to urbanization—emphasizing the creation of well-connected trade routes—reflects a holistic understanding of how infrastructure could bolster economic and social development. This legacy continues to shape Samarkand's architectural and cultural identity today.

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